

Research Appendix: Data Sources and Datasets

This appendix provides detailed references, datasets, and links to institutional sources that underpin the analysis in *Managed Forgetting*. It is designed as a technical supplement for reviewers, editors, and readers who wish to interrogate the evidence base in more depth. All sources are publicly available from government agencies, international organisations, or NGOs.

Birds and Biodiversity

British Trust for Ornithology (BTO): Breeding Bird Survey datasets and annual reports.
<https://www.bto.org/our-science/projects/bbs>

DEFRA: UK Biodiversity Indicators (annual).
<https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/uk-biodiversity-indicators>

RSPB, WWF, National Trust: State of Nature Reports. <https://stateofnature.org.uk>

Rivers and Nutrient Pollution

Environment Agency: Water quality monitoring data. <https://environment.data.gov.uk/water-quality>

European Environment Agency (EEA): Freshwater indicators, nutrients, river/lake trends.
<https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/indicators>

DEFRA: River Basin Management Plans.
<https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/river-basin-management-plans-2015>

Subsidies and Budgets

DEFRA: Farm Business Survey (FBS).
<https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/farm-business-survey>

National Audit Office: Investigations into CAP payments. <https://www.nao.org.uk>

European Court of Auditors: CAP performance and environmental reports.
<https://www.eca.europa.eu>

OECD: Agricultural Policy Monitoring and Evaluation.
<https://www.oecd.org/agriculture/topics/agricultural-policy-monitoring-and-evaluation>

Groundwater and Irrigation

Central Ground Water Board (India): Groundwater Yearbooks. <http://cgwb.gov.in>

Punjab Agriculture Department: Groundwater status and irrigation use. <http://agripb.gov.in>

FAO AQUASTAT: Global water and irrigation database. <https://www.fao.org/aquastat>

Deforestation and Land Use

INPE (Brazil): PRODES & DETER Amazon deforestation monitoring.
<http://www.obt.inpe.br/OBT/assuntos/programas/amazonia/prodes>

FAO: State of the World's Forests. <https://www.fao.org/state-of-forests>

Global Forest Watch: Tree cover loss. <https://www.globalforestwatch.org>

Nitrogen and Fertilisers

FAOSTAT: Fertiliser consumption datasets. <https://www.fao.org/faostat>

EEA: Nitrogen balance and emissions indicators.
<https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/indicators>

IPCC: Agriculture chapters in AR5 and AR6. <https://www.ipcc.ch>

Antibiotics in Agriculture

European Medicines Agency (EMA): ESVAC reports. <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en>

WHO: Global Antimicrobial Resistance Surveillance. <https://www.who.int>

EFSA/ECDC: Antimicrobial resistance in zoonotic bacteria. <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en>

Climate and Global Indicators

IPCC: Sixth Assessment Report (2021–2022). <https://www.ipcc.ch/assessment-report/ar6>

Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD): Global Biodiversity Outlook 5. <https://www.cbd.int/gbo>

World Bank: Agricultural Support Indicators.
<https://databank.worldbank.org/source/agricultural-support-indicators>